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ASSESSMENT OF RESEARCH SKILLS AMONG ACADEMIC STAFF IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN AKWA IBOM AND CROSS RIVER STATES, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study focused on assessment of research skills and practices among academic staff in public universities in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States, Nigeria. It was designed to examine the extent to which lecturers' exhibit research skills such as problem articulation, literature search, instrument construction and validation, data collection and analysis, referencing and reporting. A survey research design with an ex-post facto component was adopted with the use of multistage sampling involving simple random, stratified random and accidental sampling techniques to select 525 academic staff from public universities in the two states out of a population of 1591. The 42-item instrument, "Lecturers' ResearchSkills Questionnaire LRSQ" used for the study was triangulated with an exploratory interview to substantiate the researcher's claim for existence of the problem for the study. Cronbach alpha coefficient of .78 was obtained as an estimate of internal consistency reliability for the overall research skills measured by the instrument. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics and population t-test. The findings revealed that levels of research skills among lecturers were significantly high except data collection/analysis skill which was significantly low. Among recommendations made were the need for adequate mentoring for junior academics in research skills for improvement in quality knowledge creation. It was also recommended that regular workshops, seminars and other academic and professional meetings should be held within faculties and universities to improve research skills of academics.

Key Words: Research Skills, Academic Staff, Public Universities, Akwa Ibom State and Cross River States.

Introduction

Research has continued to be a sure way to generate new knowledge in today's knowledge-driven society. Universities and research institutes are the centers for generating this knowledge in order to ensure that the public is knowledgeable enough to bring improvement to the economy and indirectly improve the development of a country. For instance, available literature review of several studies (Asim, Kalu & Ekwueme, 2007), showed that scientific

research and development (R & D) generated by faculties of institutions of higher learning or universities more than anything else, has contributed to the rapid growth of the world knowledge economy and the transformation of the few "super" countries, particularly the "Asian tigers", that is, Japan, China, South and North Korea, Indonesia, Taiwan, Singapore, Finland and so on, over the rest of the world in the on-going globalization process. The world powers, America, Russia and Great Britain among others, have become greatly advanced technologically because of reliance on research outcome from universities and other research institutes.

Research exercise involves intellectual skills, technological/ICT skills and mechanical activities, and the university lecturers are at the center of research activities, carrying out research publications as the most significant indicator of their productivity. It may be observed that research publication in any discipline does not only provide current information for growth, progress, development but it is so significant that academic staff promotions and the social prestige attached to the increasing status up to the professorial ranks, all depend on it. In universities and research institutes alike, attainment in research is determined by the number of published articles in refereed journals, abstracted, indexed and conference proceedings of high repute.

Besides its major role as determining academic staff rewards in terms of tenure elongation, promotion and professional standing through scholarly publications, university research findings in most developing countries form the basis of major decisions and a direction for educational, technological, social and economic achievement of the country. Nigeria as one of the developing countries, has taken a very bold step in the introduction of Tertiary Education Trust fund (TETFund). This was established by the TETFund Act 2011 to administer and disburse to Federal and State Tertiary Education Institutions 2% Education tax charged companies. Nonetheless, Okpokam (2014) revealed that despite the two million naira meagre amount of the TETFund over the years, the consistency of the fund's support in terms of the availability and accessibility by the lecturers have remained inadequate. Worse still, Ikem (2011) disclosed that corruption has affected Nigeria to the extent that funds earmarked for research and development are embezzled by government officials. The above scenario tells much about academics and research carried out by them.

In recognition of its role in education, the government established the Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC), an organ that oversees research activities at the national level. Similar research institutes are established in other countries of the world: Chinese Cotton Research Institute and Academy of Science, Texas Institute of Virology, Institute of Food and Agricultural Sciences, Centre for Contagious Diseases in Africa, International Institute for Tropical Agriculture, among others, to provide solution to specific development challenges. In essence, the goals of any nation are necessarily being pursued through research activities.

Ubong and Oguzor (2005) observe that countries that have succeeded in achieving break-through are those which have invested consistently and productively not less than 2% of their Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in research and development (R&D). On the

converse, they regret that African countries unfortunately spend less than 0.5% of their GDP on (R&D). Nigeria, particularly spends only 0.1% of her Gross Domestic Product on R&D and has fifteen (15) scientists and engineers per million of her population. Japan, the foremost country in the world in the sphere of development has four thousand, nine hundred and sixty (4,960) scientists and engineers per million of her population and spends 2.8% of a much larger GDP than Nigeria, on R&D (Chukuka, 2008).

Much regard is attached to academic staff carrying out a good research. Nigeria can also be placed in a very high position as a result of contributions of the university lecturers. Good effort of these eggheads can place Nigeria in the same bracket with Japan and other super countries. The requirement there is acquisition of research skills.

Ali (2009) perceives research skill as a special ability to perform tasks or undertake a careful investigation of a phenomenon, including the ability to follow the right principles, procedures, methodologies and otherwise of a research in order to discover new knowledge for the purpose of adding to the knowledge bank. This is a part from knowledge (memory) of research skills. Therefore, research skill is developed by doing and not memorization alone. It involves also participation in conferences, seminars, workshops, symposia, collaborative researches and mentoring among others. Involvement in these and related activities fosters research skills in the individuals.

By carrying out the above, Okpe, Simisaye and Otuza (2013) alert that research is arrival at a dependable solution to a problem through collection, analysis and interpretation of data. This implies provision of a systematic procedure in getting answers to questions. Therefore, research is not an arbitrary or haphazard exercise, but follows a clearly identified, step-wise laid down procedure in arriving at dependable solution for policy influence. Generally, every step of research process involves a skill and sub-skills which range from problem identification to dissemination of findings to the target group. The possibility of undertaking a valid, reliable and useful research is enhanced when academics in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States and Nigeria in general develop the skills that enable them follow systematically the steps involved in research. These are lead ways to individual and collective capacity building for rapid national development.

Research skill development among academic staff is the engine that keeps universities to their mandate as centers of ideas and innovation for the needed development. This explains why Graduate School Programs in universities all over the world receive the much attention that are accorded them by all in the society. Masters' degree and Doctoral programs as well as other organized skill building programs by the university, exist to encourage students and their teachers alike to build up research skills as they undertake independent research including writing of theses, with supervision and guidance by the Senior Academics and Professors. In addition, as they involve in teaching and learning of structured courses involving these skills, their research skills focus could further be sharpened.

Meanwhile, there is great concern that these skills seem not to abound in most academics of universities aforementioned. In some quarters, it is being claimed that a good

number of scholars lack skills to outline existing knowledge and this has led to the collapse of adequate application of research skills in projects (Xu, Okebukola, 2008). On the other hand, much disappointments are also being expressed that today's research studies and literary works of academics show inadequacy in the in-depth analysis of generated data which could result in publication of research studies with mismatched methods of statistical techniques with the ultimate creation of ambiguity in the interpretation of research results (Bakare and Bakare, 2014).

A number of other studies exist which have attempted to expose the conflicting views about the adequacy or otherwise of skills found in the process of research. These include those of Bassey (2006), Asim, et al (2007), Hemming and Kay (2009), Ali (2009), Eze (2011), Akpabio and Uyanah (2015), Asim and Eni (2015), Joshua, Nwogwugwu and Ikiroma (2015) and Idika (2016). For instance, in the study carried out by Asim et al (2007) to determine the levels of practical skills displayed in unpublished science education graduate theses, Faculty of Education, University of Calabar and research reports in Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (JSTAN and STAN) conference proceedings, it was found that the application of the skills of problem articulation was below expectation while instrumentation skill was only marginally good, with a mean score of 1.38 which was slightly higher than the expected mean of 1.00.

In another study, Joshua et al (2015) investigated the percentage of Abia State University lecturers that possessed data analyzing research skills via SPSS and result interpreting skills from an SPSS analyzed output. The survey used 22-item structured questionnaire on a sample of 418 lecturers drawn through stratified random sampling techniques. The two research questions were answered using percentages while the hypothesis for the study was tested at .05 level of significance and df of 416 using contingency chi-square analysis. The result showed that some lecturers possessed the skills (66.8%) while others (33.2%) lacked skills in executing and interpreting data analysis. Concerning data analysis still, Umoinyang (2015) concluded that it is only these skills that can enable the researcher to obtain the summary descriptive information with which the research question can be answered and hypothesis tested. This therefore, underscores the need for lecturers to be grounded in the application of statistical method to actually excel in data analysis.

A lot more are observably being associated with academics' poor research behaviour including some fraudulent practices such as contract research paper writing, "include me in your paper syndrome" armchair investigation, patronizing quack journals among others. Unfortunately too, a careful search into many published and unpublished works indicate that there is a breach of such traditions as clear statement of problems, adequate review of literature, proper documentation, appropriate research methodology that should give rise to valid and reliable data analytic techniques and adequate interpretation of research results (Asim et al 2007; Onwioduokit, 2003).

Today, it is widely acclaimed that 60 years after the first universities were founded in Nigeria, only few publications by lecturers in universities in Nigeria are considered worthy enough for international assessment and replication (Times Higher Education Ranking,

2011). This perhaps explains the assertion of Mafuyai (2012) that the best university in Nigeria is still positioned at the rear in the world university ranking. It is therefore, an enormous challenge to worry about by lecturers and threats to the students, educational system and the society when lecturers are not able to apply the skills that they need to perform their roles as researchers, supervisors, academic advisers to the students. There is need for lecturers to imbibe the culture, attitude and skills of undertaking research objectively and effectively. It is in consideration of this that the researchers consider it imperative to access the research skills of academic staff in some public universities particularly in the two sister states, Akwa Ibom and Cross River.

This study can be framed around the self-efficacy theory of Albert Bandura which was propounded in 1997. The theory says that self-efficacy is the expectation that one has for success in a given situation (Pastorino & Doyle-Portillo, 2006). Bandura sees self-efficacy as a person's belief in his or her capability to organize and execute a task and reach a goal. In other words, efficacy beliefs affect how people think, feel, motivate themselves and act (Ogunmakin, Agbayewa and Osakuade, 2014). Major and Dolly (2013) note that self-efficacy encapsulates the way that faculty members see themselves as researchers, teachers and academic citizens as well as their belief about whether they can successfully complete tasks in each of those areas.

Bandura identified two levels of self-efficacy (high and low) which by implication can be used to predict the levels of lecturers' research skills. Going by the theory, lecturers with high self-efficacy believe that they will excel in their research skills while lecturers with low self-efficacy have low aspirations and weak commitment to research activities and, may not acquire requisite skills that will enable them to embark on meaningful research. To this group of lecturers, Iyela (2002) posits that research is just carried out for promotion; it is not in the life of the academic staff as a necessary role which must be played for university's contribution to development. Otisi (2011) further notes that many of such lecturers are skill deficient because they perceive research as a threatening and difficult activity and try to shy away from developing the skills or just engage through the work of others for purpose of academic progression. On the other hand, lecturers with higher self-efficacy who see research in its true perspective are able to cope with the great deal of efforts, resilience, and persistence required through the process to succeed. They refuse to see the procedure as a difficult task to be abandoned without requiring the skills.

Coincidentally, academic staff the world over is looked at as custodians of skills that can enable them conduct researches and come up with valid and reliable evidence which can influence policy and bring development. It is for this reason that research bodies and government as well as university management make provision for training in skills of research through forums such as seminars, workshops, symposia and conferences, encourage collaborations and mount programme in the universities through which academics could update and enhance research skills.

However, concerns are being raised about the continued poor state of research and the skills involved in its process in Nigerian universities as shown in their being continuously

ranked at the rear in the world ranking (Webometrics ranking, 2015; Times Higher Education Ranking, 2011; Mafuyai, 2012).

This is further substantiated by the findings of the exploratory interview conducted by the researchers on some willing lecturers and revealed that inadequate research skills among lecturers in the study area, if not addressed, may become a bane to effective supervision of students' research projects and dissertations and subsequent transfer of or impart of knowledge. For instance, a situation where a supervisee has to be referred to someone else for construction and validation of research instrument, statistical analysis and even formulation of research hypothesis is worrisome. Even more worrisome is a common response from the interviewees on the research skills situations in universities as "terrible". A few lecturers interviewed, described the situation of inadequacy of research skills as "helpless".

Invariably, if the present scenario is allowed to persist as it is growing rapidly; students may continually be graduated with challenges that may be obviously spell doom for our future educational system and the economy as a whole. Consequently, students may not be able to compete with global requirements, which imply that the national demand of lecturers to teach students to acquire knowledge and develop skills for effective research (FRN, 2008) may never be met. This may cause the much needed breakthrough tied to research to remain unrealized. It is an attempt to seek solution to the problem of inadequate skills that has motivated this study.

The general purpose was to assess the research skills of academic staff in Universities in AKS and CRS. Specifically, the study sought to examine the extent to which lecturer's exhibit research skills in terms of:

- Problem articulation, Literature search, Instrument development and validation, Data collection and analysis, Referencing and Reporting

Ho: The levels of research skills exhibited by academic staff of universities in AKS and CRS on problem articulation, literature search, instrument development and validation, data collation and analysis, referencing and reporting are not significantly high.

The research design adopted for this study was a survey with an ex-post facto component. As a survey, it involved a collection of data from a segment (sample) considered to be representative of the entire group (population). The design therefore, permits the drawing of inference about the population based on sample evidence. The ex-post facto component of the study is explained by the fact that research skills have naturally occurred in the setting among lecturers and therefore, they were only described and not manipulated by the researchers in the course of this study.

The study adopted multistage sampling involving simple random, stratified random and accidental sampling techniques to select 525 academic staff from public universities in the two states out of the population of 1591. The first stage involved the use of simple random sampling. This was to enable the researcher to select four faculties from each of the

universities (Table 1). This resulted to a total of sixteen faculties that were utilized in this study.

Table 1: Sampled Faculties in UNICAL, CRUTECH, UNIUYO and AKSU.

S/N	FACULTY	UNICAL	CRUTECH	UNIUYO	AKSU	TOTAL
1	Education	209	49	133	62	453
2	Management science	84	24	120	46	427
3	Social Science/Env. Science	129	40	105	33	307
4	Science	227	73	175	82	557
	Total	649	186	533	223	1,591

Source: Academic Staff Establishment/ Planning Unit of UNICAL, UNIUYO, CRUTECH and AKSU, September, 2014.

The second stage was the use of stratified random sampling technique. In each university, the four faculties that were randomly sampled constituted the strata (i.e each faculty a stratum).

The third stage was the use of accidental sampling to reach the respective lecturers in the faculties. This was because it was practically difficult to bring all faculty members together to use any probabilistic sampling approach. Due to the size of the population and the purpose of this study, the researchers decided to use a convenient sample of 33% to enable proportionality of the faculty members since they do not have the same population size. Using this approach, the researchers obtained the sample of 525. The study involved the use of researcher developed instrument called "Lecturers' Research Skills Questionnaire LRSQ" which was triangulated with an exploratory interview conducted by the researchers for data to substantiate the claim for inadequate research skills. The instrument contained 42 items which were judged adequate by two measurement experts and one expert in educational planning and administration. The first six items were used to measure problem articulation; 7 - 12 items measured literature search; 13 - 18 items measured instrument construction and validation. Eight items each were used to measure data collection/analysis, reporting and referencing. The instrument consisted of a 10-point Guttman scale with a maximum score of 10 and a minimum of 1. In order to adjudge the first three levels of research skills (problem articulation, literature search and instrument development and validation) significantly high, the sample mean on each skill was to be significantly greater than the reference score of 33.00 (which was the average of the 10-point scale multiplied by six items of each sub-skill). That is, $1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10/10=5.5 \times 6$. On the other hand, for the last three sub-skills (data collection and analysis, referencing and reporting) the sample mean of each was to be significantly greater than the reference score of 44.00 (ie, average of the scale 5.5, multiplied by 8 items in each sub-skill). That is, $1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10/10=5.5 \times 8$. In the case of the overall research skills, the sample mean was to be significantly greater than the reference score of 231 (5.5 x 42 research skill items). The face validity of the instrument was therefore, established as a result of the high level of agreement among the three groups of experts. Its content validity was also ensured through thorough vetting by three research and

measurement experts. The LRSQ was pilot tested to determine its reliability and its internal consistency was established using Cronbach alpha with an estimate of .78.

The data collection was done with the help of three doctoral students in Research, Measurement and Evaluation Unit, who also assisted in conveying the instrument. The Deans of the selected faculties also constituted part of the research assistants. This was because the instruments were deposited in the Deans' offices where the actual accidental sampling took place. As lecturers visited the Dean's office for one thing or the other, such lecturers were requested to respond to the instrument. This continued until the determined sample size of each faculty was obtained. The administration of the instrument lasted for a period of one month as most lecturers were involved in other activities outside the offices and could not be reached within a short period to retrieve the questionnaires. However, only 504 out of 525 were retrieved (96% return rate). Thus, making the actual sample used for data analysis to be 504. All the returned questionnaires were anonymously completed. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and population t-test of version 20 of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The result is presented as follows:

Result:

Table 2: One sample t-test result of the analysis of the levels of research skills exhibited by academic staff of Universities in AKS and CRS (N= 504)

S/N	Research skills	$\bar{X}$	μ	SD	t-value	df	P-value
1.	Problem articulation	36.88	33.00	8.57	70.43*	503	.000
2.	Literature search	33.01	33.00	7.13	65.06*	503	.000
3.	Instrument development and validation	34.57	33.00	8.17	74.06*	503	.001
4.	Data collection and analysis	36.77	44.00	7.13	-68.54*	503	.000
5.	Referencing	44.61	44.00	8.04	79.03*	503	.001
6.	Reporting	45.25	44.00	7.00	71.07*	503	.000
7.	Overall research skills	38.52	38.50	7.67	69.75*	503	.002

* $P < .05$, $df_{(503)}$, $t_{critical} = 1.960$

X = Sample mean. μ = Reference mean, SD = Sample standard deviation

From Table 2, lecturers' problem articulation is significantly high ($t = 70.43$; $p < .05$); literature search is significantly high ($t = 65.06$; $p < .05$); instrument development and validation is significantly high ($t = 74.06$; $p < .05$); data collection and analysis is significantly low ($t = -68.54$; $p < .05$); referencing skill is significantly high ($t = 79.03$; $p < .05$); reporting is significantly high ($t = 71.07$; $p < .05$) and the overall research skill is significantly high ($t = 69.75$; $p < .05$). Hence the null hypothesis that the levels of research skills exhibited by academic staff of universities on problem articulation, literature search, instrument

development and validation, data collection and analysis, referencing and reporting, are not significantly high is rejected at the .05 level of significance. It is only in the case of data collection and analysis that this hypothesis is upheld. That is, the negative t-value associated with data collection and analysis is an indication that lecturers' research skills in this area are significantly low.

Discussions

The findings as shown in Table 2 indicate that academic staff in universities in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States exhibited high level of research skills except in the case of data collection and analysis where a negative t-value was recorded, indicating a significant low level of research skill exhibition in that area. However, weighed against the popular views of many authors found in the literature about the level of research competence and output in Nigeria, this findings can be said to be a surprise. For instance, Otisi (2011), Okebukola (2008), Hemmings and Kay (2009), Chiemekwe, Longe and Shaib (2009), Duzer (2010) among others, who claimed that several challenges face the research industry which make only few publications by university lecturers in Nigeria to be considered worthy enough for international assessment and replication.

However, the overall performance of academic staff as revealed in this study may find explanation in the theoretical principle of high self-efficacy of Albert Bandura and this is not unconnected with the findings of Archibong, Ogbiji and Anijaobi-Idem (2010), Mafuyai (2012). The authors regretted the poor research environment of Nigerian academics, and noted that even the non-provision of adequate facilities for research, non-functionality of and overcrowding of available facilities, security situation of our campuses etc, academic staff notably create their own research environment and privately sponsor themselves to workshops, seminars and conferences locally and internationally. All these enable them acquire research skills needed for attainment of research excellence. In connection with this, is the findings of Bassey, et al (2007), that showed that lecturers in universities in the world over, work hard to publish so as to gain recognition and advancement in their profession. These altogether may have motivated lecturers to exhibit high levels of most of the research skills as revealed by the result of this hypothesis.

With respect to the levels of research skills exhibition on problem articulation, the results showed significantly high application indicating that lecturers in AKS and CRS have exhibited this skill. This finding agrees with Ali (2009) and Eze (2011), who found all the components of problem articulation skills to be significantly high. This is an indication too, that lecturers in the study area are aware of importance of problem articulation as a critical stage in the process of research that needs to be acquired and exhibited properly and effectively. Moreso, research is a scientific activity that is driven by imaginative thinking, agility, creative, logical and conceptual reasoning. A possible explanation for the high mean score ($\bar{X}$ = 36.88) in this skill could be an increased awareness of the need to possess innovative skills for quality research in solving life's problem.

These findings however, seem to disagree with the assertion from the findings of Asim et al, (2007), Akpabio and Uyanah (2015) and Asim & Eni (2015) who unanimously expressed the poor background of researches done in our universities to be attributed to inadequate display of problem articulation skills in conference proceedings, inadequate capacity to appropriate conceptual and theoretical framework and ignorance of the significance of assumptions in research studies. It is on the basis of this evidence that Asim et al (2007), suggested that the peer- review of articles sent for publication in conference proceedings should pay serious attention to problem articulation and its description. This also presupposes that more encouragement for training of staff in this skill be ensured. The need for acquiring more skills of problem articulation could be shown with the fact that the process of every research begins with problem articulation; therefore, the output of research can hardly be anything better than its beginning.

On the extent of staff exhibition of literature search skills, the findings as revealed by Table 2 indicate that the levels were significantly high. The calculated t-value (65.06) was found to be significantly higher than the critical value of t (1.96). On the other hand the result shows that the mean performance of academics in this skill (as indicated by the small difference between $\bar{X}$ and μ) is not adequate. This finding is in agreement with Eze (2011) in the study on assessment of research skills among the nurses in CRS Health Institutions which found the application of literature review skills to be inadequate. The result further agrees with Shkedi (1998) using teachers as sample which found low competence among the subjects in the use of search literature to expand professional knowledge and solve problems. The results also find support in Archibong and Effiom (2009), Archibong et al (2010) and Duze (2010) which observed low performance in the skills examined to be adduced to ill equipped libraries and laboratories, poor and irregular supply of electricity, inadequate training programme and other unsupportive research environment. However, recommendation for efficient professional training through regular workshops, seminars and conferences as means of improving skills were made by some researchers with regard to this observation (Carlson and Gadion, 2002; Joshi, Pradhan and Dixit, 2003; Egbo, 2011). All the same, the present researchers have noted that the low performance is a factor that could shift ground when more academic staff would have been conversant with the new technological breakthrough called ICT which has enhanced the practices of their counterparts in a more adequately provided ICT environments.

The findings of the study as indicated in Table 2 have shown the level of research skills exhibited by academics staff in terms of instrument development and validation to be significantly high. Although the calculated t-value (74.06) was found to be greater than the table t-test value (1.96), from the result, the sample mean for this skill was found to be one of the least. For the mean performance, the findings indicated that skill of instrumentation was only marginally applied by academic staff in the study area. This finding is in agreement with Asim, et al. (2007), who discovered in their study on skills in unpublished researches in science education, that the practical skills as displayed in the report of instrumentation in conference proceedings to be good though marginally.

The study finding also corroborates Ikeh and Ifeanyieze (2015) who concluded that the challenge facing most researchers is determining what instrument that suits a particular study that is being handled. Agreeing with the above, Mazaduand Zuhumben (2014) noted too that the challenge included that of developing the technical expertise required for construction of valid instrument. These challenges have great implication for this study. Many academic staff confronted with these problems, may readily prefer the option of adopting an existing instrument atmost with modifications rather than accepting to be trained to develop their instruments. Psychological measurement experts such as Nenty and Umoinyang (2005), Joshua (2005), have emphasized the need for developing valid and reliable instruments for measurements that will yield dependable research results. The assessment of skills needed for this purpose among academic staff is a major consideration of this study.

However, studies that contradict these findings are not found in the literature reviewed for this study. More so, the scarce literature could be adduced to non reporting of the detailed research instruments of many studies which makes most of these works (instruments) inaccessible for evaluation by researchers.

The level of research skill exhibition among academic staff in terms of data collection and analysis was significant, with a negative t-value. This is to say that though there is a difference, it shows in a negative way indicating that lecturers' research skills in this area are significantly low. This is an indication that a good number of academic staff in the population have not exhibited these important skills efficiently and appropriately in course of their research activities. This finding is in line with the thinking of Umoinyang (2015), in his opinion paper on data analysis. He posited that the skill to gather data and carry out analysis of data though inadequate among researchers, has remained basic and therefore, inevitable if a dependable research result must be realized.

The mean score for data collection and analysis (36.77) is significantly lower than the hypothesized value of 44.00 ($t = 1.96$; $p < .05$) an indication that the exhibition the skill of data collection and analysis by the lecturers was not up to expectation. It is also an indication that the extent of exhibition of this skill may not have been spread among the subjects involved in this study, meaning that while some lecturers exhibited the skills, some others lacked the skills. This finding agrees with Joshua, et al (2015), who investigated the percentage of Abia State University lecturers that possessed data analyzing research skills and result of interpreting data from the analyzed output, and discovered that while some lecturers possessed skills, others were found lacking.

The finding of this study also bears relevance with the result of Eze (2011) which showed significant low application of statistical analysis of data ($t = -33.59$). It was shown in this study that in terms of choice of suitable statistical analysis, researchers' application of research skills was inadequate. The findings of Ali (2009), Campbell (2000) and Eze (2011), are in agreement with the result of this study. The authors concluded that adequate application of statistics, result interpretation, choice of statistics and application which are lacking among some researchers often lead to wrong interpretation of results and

conclusions. It is important to note that if lecturers lack the expertise to make choice of data collection or analysis approach, or to carry out the actual analysis from screening and coding instruments up to computer output analysis, or the skills to even categorize, order, manipulate and summarize data, it may become difficult to obtain answers to research questions and results of hypothesis testing. This undoubtedly may be a reason why findings of some researches in education and other disciplines may not have found use in quarters where they could relevantly influence policies and programs of activities. It is believed that the findings of this study will help to breach the gap between research evidence and policy of government in education.

The results in Table 2 shows that the level of research skills exhibition among academic staff in terms of referencing was found to be significantly high. The calculated t-value (79.03) was higher than the critical value of t (1.96) at .05 level. This study result somewhat confirms the findings of Ali (2009), which showed that application of skill of referencing was significantly high. This is not unexpected especially as academic staff members are conscious of academic dishonesty in the area of plagiarism and ethical considerations. Moreso, the magnitude of plagiarism detection has become widespread and with anti-plagiarism device, such as the turn-it-in software and others emerging in the scene, there seems to be very little or no escape route for defaulters. These perhaps have helped lecturers and supervisors of research to seek means to upgrade and improve their research skills in this area, hence, the outcome of this result tend to be in conformity with this observation.

Nevertheless, from the result of this findings, this skill has been rated next to reporting which was the most exhibited with respect to the means ($\bar{X} = 44.61$ and $\mu = 44.00$). The result also showed that academic staff's performance though good, in this skill was only marginal. This could be as a result of an already observed reason that academics require capacity building in the areas of low competence such as referencing. Many observations in this regard suggest that lecturers need to put on the attitude of conscientiousness (i.e. professional responsibility, honesty, courtesy) towards research activities. (Isangedighi, 2012; Eukoha et al, 2005).

The level of research skills exhibited by academic staff in terms of reporting as shown in Table 2 was found to be significantly high. The calculated t-value (71.07) was found to be higher than the critical t-value of 1.96 at .05 alpha level. This finding confirms the study of Ali (2009) and is also in tune with the views of many opinions in literature. While the results of Ali (on evaluation of extent of application of research skills of reporting) was found to be significantly high and in support, the findings of Hagger and McIntyre(2000), Davies (2000), and Eukoha et al (2005), have emphasized the critical role of reporting in education research. Efficient reporting of research findings by academic staff and other educators can help to better professional knowledge about school management and effective teaching and learning. This is because a lot of good, well-rounded research evidence will be communicated into key policy issues.

In terms of the mean performances of sampled and referenced, it can be shown from the result that the difference is only marginal. The academics' mean exhibition of the skill of reporting was therefore, not far different from the expected ($\bar{X} = 43.76$; $\mu = 44.00$). This could mean that even though the skill of reporting appeared to be the most applied (that is skill with the highest mean of 45.25), yet, it shows a performance that is not too encouraging, implying that lecturers in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States need to be equipped with more skills in this area. This could be achieved through seminars, workshops, symposia, collaborations, mentoring and the like. On the whole, the high t-values associated with the sub-skills as seen in Table 2 may be attributed to methodological and analytical use of self-report instrument (questionnaire) and Statistical Package for Social Sciences. It is therefore, important that other researchers take the findings with caution. Future researches in this area could concentrate on the use of content analysis or lecturers' published work.

Conclusion

The study assessed the research skills of lecturers in universities in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States in the areas of problem articulation, literature search, instrument development and validation, data collection and analysis, referencing and reporting. The overall skills in the process of research exhibited by faculty members in the study area are significantly high. This justified the outcome of this research on lecturer's performance in the individual skills as shown in being able to match the criterion (expected) level of skills exhibition in this study, perhaps with the exception of data collection and analysis. The study has therefore, provided a baseline data on research skills of academics which can give an insight into areas of capacity building.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Regular workshops, seminars and other academic and professional meetings should be organized within faculties and universities where lecturers could be trained to enhance their research skills.
- ii. Encouragement of academic staff to attend and fully participate in conferences, seminars and workshops regularly organized in departments, faculties within and outside the universities. This could be achieved by giving adequate financial support to the staff on one hand and attaching much recognition to the evidence (certificate of attendance and participation) acquired from such academic involvements.
- iii. Senior academics should adequately mentor the junior lecturers so that their research skills could be sharpened.
- iv. University is the centre of research excellence. Therefore, employment of lecturers with research interest and expertise should be paramount. In recruiting academic staff, the Research, Statistics and Measurement units/departments of universities should be deeply involved in predicting the research capabilities of these would be lecturers. This is to ensure that as the employees are coming in to add to the junior

staff members, they already have positive orientation towards research right from the onset.

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